

TABLE 2—RESULTS OBTAINED USING INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

Name of International standards used	Values obtained by the present method (ppm)				Recommended values (ppm)			
	Ag	Bi	Mo	V	Ag	Bi	Mo	V
Soil SO-4	0.001-0.01	0.01-0.1	0.1-1.0	10-100	n.i.	0.1	1.0	90 ^a
Peridotite PCC-1	0.001-0.01	0.01-0.1	0.1-1.0	10-100	0.005	0.013	0.2	30 ^b
Gabbro MRG-1	0.1-1.0	0.1-1.0	1.0-10	>100	0.14	n.i.	n.i.	520 ^c

n.r. = Not reported. ^aRef. 2. ^bRef. 3. ^cRef. 4.

that of the known standards, the amount of the four elements in the unknown was easily obtained.

Instrumentation: Into the crucible containing the ash, the flux (15 mg) containing Sp-2 graphite powder and lithium carbonate (A.R) in the proportion of 1:1 were added, and was transferred completely to a small agate mortar (50 mm dia) with the help of a brush and ground well with agate pestle. The whole mass was then transferred to the crater of a graphite electrode with the help of a funnel and weighing paper. The electrode (4.57 mm dia) used was of Union Carbide make. The crater was of 8 mm depth and 3.2 mm dia. The crater containing the sample was kept under i.r. lamp for an hour and arced using a counter electrode of 3.04 mm dia and coned to 60°.

The arcing was carried out in a 1.5 Meter Wadsworth Spectrograph (Jarrel-Ash) at a current of 10 A dc for 60 s. The arcing gap was adjusted 3 mm throughout and slit width used was 10 microns. Development and fixing of the spectrum was done for 3 min at 72°F using Kodak developer and fixer. Stop bath was used for 30 s at 72°F. Drying of the film was carried out in an automatic photoprocessor.

Results and Discussion

Silver was estimated by studying its spectral intensity at 3280.683 Å, bismuth at 3067.716 Å, molybdenum at 3170.347 Å and vanadium at 3185.396 Å. The results of analysis are those values which lie between two adjacent values of the standards.

International standards have been analysed by this procedure and the results obtained were found very satisfactory. The results are shown in Table 2. The procedure has been found to be accurate for estimation of Ag, Bi, Mo and V in parts per billion levels, and is less costly.

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Naphthalein Scarlet-4RS—an Amperometric Reagent for Trace Determination of Rare Earths

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NAPHTHALEIN scarlet-4RS a metallochromic indicator has been known to form complexes with transition metals and rare earths¹. The dye produces a blood red colour in acidic medium which makes it useful as a spectrophotometric reagent for the estimation of various metal ions. In continuation of the work in our laboratory on the trace estimation of transition metals and rare earths²⁻⁶ using amperometric titration technique, the present paper discusses a procedure for the estimation of rare earths with naphthalein scarlet-4RS, using a d.m.e.—Hg pool electrode system.

Experimental

Solutions of trivalent rare earths (La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Eu, Er, Tb, Dy) were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of the rare earth (oxides/nitrates) in a calculated amount of perchloric acid/water and standardised². The solution of naphthalein scarlet-4RS was prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of the reagent in conductivity water. Amperometric titrations were done on a manually operated polarograph with a multiflex galvanometer (sensitivity 8.1×10^{-9} A/div.) using d.m.e. as an indicator electrode and Hg-pool as reference electrode, the capillary characteristics in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KCl being $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.136 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$. The amperometric titrations were performed at room temperature

$20 \pm 0.1^\circ$. For titrations, a number of solutions containing calculated amount of rare earths in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KCl as supporting electrolyte were prepared. pH of the test solutions was adjusted to 6.5 ± 0.02 using dilute HCl/NaOH solutions, on a Elico L1-120 digital pH meter.

Results and Discussion

Naphthalein scarlet-4RS gives a well defined cathodic reduction wave. The height of the diffusion current is proportional to the concentration of the dye.

The plateau potential of naphthalein scarlet-4RS - 0.90 V (vs Hg-pool), at which rare earths do not give any wave, was applied. A standard solution of rare earth was added dropwise from a semimicro burette. The current was noted on the multiflex galvanometer after each addition of the rare earth aliquot. On plotting a graph between galvanometer deflection and added titrant volume (after necessary volume correction), a L-shaped curve was obtained. The end-point of titration indicated metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 1, which is in good agreement with the results reported in the literature¹. Reversed L-shaped curves may be obtained by choosing naphthalein scarlet-4RS as titrant.

It was observed that 100-fold concentration of ions, i.e. Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , chloride, chlorate, nitrate, acetate and sulphate do not interfere in the titration procedure. However, a small amount of Ag^+ , Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , VO^{2+} , MoO_4^{2-} , and carbonate ions interfere with the titration seriously.

Ultramicro and microgram quantities of La, Ce, Pr, Sm, Nd, Er, Tb, Gd and Dy have been separately estimated amperometrically, with in an error of less than $\pm 0.8\%$.

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Studies on Macroreticular Cation-exchangers

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ION-EXCHANGERS are generally manufactured from various organic chemicals and hence, there is an increase in the cost of these materials. In order to minimise the cost of the chemicals as well as the cost of ion-exchangers, various materials¹, like rice husk², bagasse³ and coconut fibre⁴ etc., were converted into charcoal in our laboratory. The present work is an attempt to prepare cation-exchangers with charcoal obtained from groundnut shells.

Experimental

Phenol and formaldehyde (B.D.H.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (sp.gr. 1.82) were used. Groundnutshell procured locally, was powdered and cleaned before use.

Phenol (10 g) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (12.5 ml) were mixed slowly with constant cooling and then heated to about 100° on a water-bath for 3 h, cooled immediately in ice and kept overnight.

Sulphonated groundnut charcoal was added to phenol-sulphuric acid mixture so as to keep the percentage of substitution of groundnut shell charcoal at 0, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50 and 100. Each mixture was polymerised with formaldehyde (12.5 ml) at 70° to yield a reddish brown powder, which was grounded, sieved and preserved for further work. These constitute the samples labelled A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H and I.

The average swelling percentage and the absolute density are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PERCENTAGE SWELLING AND ABSOLUTE DENSITIES

Sample no.	Percentage of groundnut shell charcoal in resin	Average swelling percentage	Absolute density	
			In the hydrated state	In the dehydrated state
A	0	80.40	1.48	1.37
B	20	76.50	1.47	1.36
C	25	75.40	1.40	1.35
D	30	74.80	1.38	1.35
E	35	73.50	1.37	1.27
F	40	70.90	1.31	1.17
G	45	68.40	1.30	1.15
H	50	67.80	1.21	1.11
J	100	49.00	1.15	1.10

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